

REPORT D2.2

Policy briefings for policymakers for the implementation of the multi- actor approach

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PREMIERE –
PREPARING MULTI-ACTOR PROJECTS
IN A CO-CREATIVE WAY

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ACRONYMS

Acronym	Long Form
AKIS	Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy of the EU
EU CAP Network	European Network of the Common Agricultural Policy
D	Deliverable (report)
DG	Directorate General of the European Commission
DG RTD	General Directorate for Research, Technology and Digitalisation
DG GROW	General Directorate for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs
EC	European Commission
EIP-AGRI	European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability
ESR	Evaluation Summary Report
EU	European Union
FG	Focus Group
HEU	Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme
ISS	Innovation Support Services
MA	Multi-actor
MAA	Multi-actor approach
NCP	National Contact Point (of a National Research Ministry)
REA	European Research Executive Agency
RPI	Reporting Period 1 of PREMIERE, month 1 - month 18
R&I	EU Commission's Research and Innovation (R&I) framework
SCAR AKIS SWG	Strategic Working Group of the Standing Committee on Agricultural Research for Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems
T	Task in the work plan of a HEU project
WP	Work Package in the work plan of a HEU project

SUMMARY POINTS FOR D2.2

- The Horizon 2020 Programme (2014-2020) included 93 topics and 229 projects that required the application of MAA (24% of all H2020 Cluster 6 Projects).
- This Deliverable D2.2 with its Annex documents presents the results of the work related to implementing the MAA.
- D2.2 addresses key areas of interest for implementing the MAA in the. (In contrast, D2.1 focused on the level of the programming)
- The aspects addressed refer to the operational activities the analysis of the Evaluation Summary Reports prepared by external experts who were involved in the proposal assessment (ESR analysis with MA Rubric in Annex I); and the provision of information on potential applicants compiled in a 'Question and Answer' (Q&A) document in Annex II of D2.2.
- All results prepared will feed into discussion and documents, which are ongoing and will continue to evolve.
- This approach of presenting 'draft' versions of up-to-date briefing documents aims to trigger discussion and was identified as a particular strength of the PREMIERE project during the first interim project review after the end of Reporting Period RP1. This 'step-wise' methodological approach will continue.
- The qualitative and quantitative analysis of the ESRs shows that the quality of the evaluation process related to the MAA developed positively. This means the clarity and correctness of statements describing the MA assessment became more convincing in recent years compared to the early years around 2015. Evaluators have improved their MA understanding and the competencies to express the MA aspects assessed in their Evaluation Summary Reports (ESR) in Horizon Europe.
- The target groups are more or less experienced potential Beneficiaries of MAA Call Topics, Advisors of public or private institutes providing support for proposal developers, Evaluators, EC Officers, national Policy stakeholders, and Advisors/Trainers/Educators involved in proposal preparation and associated information events.
- The overview of positive and negative evaluation statements of successful and rejected applications gives excellent insights into how the MAA was assessed by the external reviewers. Lots of lessons can be learnt from the presentation of the different evaluation statements.
- During info or brokerage events, participants ask MA-specific questions. The Q&A document aims to present a set of practice-oriented explanations that serve as a resource of basic answers for novices unfamiliar with MAA.

1 INTRODUCTION

The project PREMIERE (Preparing multi-actor projects in a co-creative way) is a European Union (EU) Horizon Europe (HEU) that aims to strengthen the multi-actor approach (MAA) by supporting the development of more relevant, coherent, and well-prepared project proposals¹.

This Deliverable D2.2 on policy work (implementing) is part of Work Package (WP) 2 – ‘Background, (financial) support, and evaluation’, which aims to contribute to ensuring the enabling environment for effective implementation of the MAA in the Framework Programme of Horizon Europe (HEU). The objective is to make the governance structures and processes for multi-actor (MA) implementation ‘fit for purpose’. PREMIERE’s WP2 team aims to develop institutional-level guidelines for two levels of governance: policymakers in charge of the MAA programming and those responsible for its implementation.

This Deliverable D2.2 with its Annex documents presents the results of the work related to the implementation of the MAA. D2.2 is mutually connected with D2.1, submitted at the end of Reporting Period 1. It highlights the insights gained and draft recommendations developed from the work in the first 18 months of the PREMIERE project (submitted in mid-July 2024). While D2.1 focused on the higher policy level (also called ‘macro-level governance’ in the PREMIERE DoA), D2.2 addresses key areas of interest of the so-called ‘meso-level governance’ or the programme implementation related to the MAA in the Horizon Europe Programme. The aspects addressed refer to the operational activities e.g. proposal evaluation and selection included in the ESR analysis (Annex I), as well as the provision of general advice to potential applicants compiled in the ‘Question and Answer’ (Q&A) document (Annex II). The set of questions addressed was collected from a sample of questions that participants asked at different info or brokerage events. These were held in the second half of 2023 by DG-AGRI or REA.

Deliverable 2.2 presents a snapshot of the ongoing engagement with policy and administrative officers in charge of implementing the MAA in Horizon Europe projects. For that reason, the submission of these briefing documents presents an output of the ongoing work in progress. For example, the early insights from the ESR analysis in 2023 fed directly into the MA-related explanations given in 2023 but were deepened throughout the project in 2024. The work will

¹ see <https://premiere-multiactor.eu/>

continue because the context of the MAA in the European innovation project funding is evolving. For that reason, also the support-oriented work with e.g., policy advice of the PREMIERE team will remain flexible and adjust to the emerging needs of its target groups. In this sense, D2.2 is (like D2.1) a status report at a relatively early time during the lifetime of the project. All reflections presented and documents prepared will feed into discussion and documents, which will continue to evolve. This approach of presenting ‘draft’ versions of up-to-date briefing documents, to trigger discussion, has been identified as a particular strength of the PREMIERE project during the first interim project review after the end of Reporting Period RP1. This ‘step-wise’ methodological approach will continue.

The two annexed documents of D2.2 are the results of the ongoing consultation and support process. The core document of report D2.2 consists of four sections, which outline 1) the importance and evolution of the MAA and its growing role in the European Framework Programmes; 2) the target groups addressed by the briefings, 3) the purpose and key elements/findings of the policy briefing products; and 4) the next steps planned.

The report presents the analyses done so far and the status quo of results focusing on the ‘meso-level’ policy work in two so-called policy briefing documents:

- Annex I) Consideration of the MAA in Evaluation Summary Reports (ESR): from analysis to a quality rubric
- Annex II) Detailed Questions and Answers (Q&A) about the MAA.

2 IMPORTANCE OF THE MULTI-ACTOR APPROACH IN HORIZON EUROPE PROJECTS

The ‘Interactive Innovation Approach’ (IIA) is a core element of the AKIS and the EIP-AGRI concepts. It aims at increasing the projects’ impact by starting by identifying the end user's needs and creating co-ownership during the project for all involved². The model is based on the MAA that involves all relevant actors with complementary backgrounds and expertise to co-create and share knowledge, best practices, and innovative solutions responding to the needs of the users such as farmers, foresters, and advisors throughout the project. The MAA is considered a form of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), aiming to make the R&I process and its outcomes more demand-driven,

² EU SCAR AKIS (2019), Preparing for Future AKIS in Europe. Brussels, European Commission.

reliable, and relevant to society, and to achieve a much quicker and bigger impact in practice than in the past.

The MAA was first introduced in 2014 under Horizon 2020. Since then, it has been continuously improved based on experiences, and on evaluators', Member States' and stakeholders' feedback of applicants, project coordinators and other experts, including the discussions within the SCAR AKIS Strategic Working Group.

The Horizon 2020 Programme (2014-2020) included 93 topics and 229 projects that required the application of MAA (24% of all H2020 Cluster 6 Projects³). The MAA was applied almost exclusively to topics that concerned the agricultural and forestry sectors in the Horizon 2020 work programmes of the Societal Challenge 2 – Food security, Sustainable agriculture and forestry, Marine and maritime and inland water research, and the Bioeconomy (SC2).

Under Horizon Europe (2021-2027), the MAA has been opened to all sectors under Cluster 6 going beyond agriculture, forestry and rural areas. Currently, the MAA requirement also applies to topics related to food systems, bioeconomy, environment, fisheries and aquaculture, etc. As a result, the number of topic calls with the compulsory application of the MAA has notably increased. In Cluster 6 of the Work Programme in the period 2021-2023, 126 topics with a total of 216 projects required the application of the MAA, which represents around 45% of all Cluster 6 Calls). Besides Cluster 6, the MAA has been applied to the Horizon Soil and Oceans Missions as well as in the Calls of several Horizon Partnerships, including 'Agroecology', 'Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking' and 'PRIMA-Mediterranean'.

The MAA has been also further reinforced over time. During the Horizon 2020 period, the MAA has officially become an eligibility criterion. In addition, the definition and requirements of the MAA included in the introduction of the Work Programme⁴ have been revised and simplified. The main actors that are required to be involved in the projects are indicated in the scope of the topics. The term 'end-user(s)' indicates the person(s) putting the project results into practice.

³ According to Horizon Dashboard 926 grant agreements were signed in all H2020 Cluster 6. <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/horizon-dashboard>

⁴ Horizon Europe Cluster 6 WP 2023-2024, p. 21-23: [wp-9-food-bioeconomy-natural-resources-agriculture-and-environment horizon-2023-2024_en.pdf](#) (europa.eu)

Figure 1. Number of ESRs according to the quality of statements referring to the MAA

PREMIERE’s policy work will show that the quality of the evaluation process of MA proposals in the statements of the Evaluation Summary Reports (ESR)⁵ has increased between programmes. Figure 1 shows the comparison between H2020 (orange bars) and HEU (blue bars) in a study sample of 67 ESRs. While in H2020 42% of ESRs were of accurate or best quality in respect to the assessment of the MAA, this percentage increased to 68% in HEU. The ESR analysis shows that the quality of assessments has improved with 55% of good or best ESR statements on MAA.

3 TARGET GROUPS OF THE D2.2 POLICY BRIEFING DOCUMENTS

The target groups of the ESR report (Annex I) are the following:

- Potential beneficiaries of MAA Call Topics such as project coordinators and participants. They can benefit from the rubric when developing proposals.
- Advisors provide training and support in the designing, writing, and revising of proposal documents. These are e.g., public agencies such as NCPs or private consultants.
- Evaluators of MAA proposals and responsible EC officers stand to gain from the rubric, as this briefing document includes a section specifically

⁵ The Evaluation Summary Report (ESR) is the final resulting document of a Horizon proposal evaluation process.

designed for structuring the evaluation of MAA-related content. This ensures evaluators assess proposals effectively.

- Policy stakeholders in charge of drafting Call Topics can use the rubric to align the Topic texts more closely to the MAA requirement than in earlier Call Topic paragraphs.
- Lastly, advisors and trainers involved in proposal preparation, including those providing guidance during InfoDays or through dedicated training and consulting activities. They can use the rubric to support coordinators to ensure a consistent implementation of the MAA in their project design.

This list of target groups fits well with the seven target group Profiles of PREMIERE, which the consortium co-designed at the beginning of the second project year. These Profiles go beyond the clustering by professional activities as shown above because they also include the level of MA expertise and attitudes towards implementing the MAA. Therefore, the PREMIERE Profiles help to develop tailor-made communication, dissemination and stakeholder involvement strategies for the different project years or periods. (For more information, see PREMIERE Profiles I to VII in D1.3 ‘Experiences from the Stakeholder Dialogues’). Referring to the PREMIERE Profiles, this D2.2 report targets the following user groups:

- Profile III: Various actors involved in earlier multi-actor projects
- Profile IV: Innovation support services (ISS), CAP networks, NCPs, and other multi-actor support services
- Profile V: National/regional policy and admin officials
- Profile VI: REA, project evaluators

The target groups of the Q&A briefing document (Annex II) include all the PREMIERE Profiles presented in D1.3.

- For novice practitioners (Profile I) and novice researchers/advisors (Profile II), it offers guidance on applying MAA principles and understanding project requirements.
- Experienced actors (Profile III) can use it to refine their approach to MA projects and to explain the particular proposal-specific approach to MA novices in their proposal consortium.
- Publicly funded support services (Profile IV) such as ISS, national CAP network officials, and NCPs might use it to provide advice to newcomers or less-experienced MA proposal developers.
- Policymakers and administrators (Profiles V & VI) benefit from insights on aligning national and EU innovation programmes with MAA requirements. The Q&A document can serve as a useful tool supporting InfoDays, which

are usually held soon after the publication of the next round of Horizon Europe Calls.

- Lastly, contracting authorities and officers with an MA focus (Profile VII) can use the Q&A document to enhance the evaluation and implementation of MA principles.

4 PURPOSE, KEY ELEMENTS AND FINDINGS OF POLICY BRIEFING OUTPUT

The policy work presented in this report includes the Evaluation Summary Report and the Q&A on the MAA document, which provide guidance and tools for a diverse range of stakeholders involved in MA projects, from novice practitioners to policymakers and evaluators.

The policy work presented in this report includes two outcomes, targeted to actors (described above) who are in charge of the programme implementation as well as to potential beneficiaries of the funded projects with MAA:

- **Consideration of the MAA in Evaluation Summary Reports (ESR): from analysis to a quality rubric.** This briefing document provides an evaluation of the MAA projects within Horizon 2020 and HEU through a detailed review of 67 ESRs. It advocates for the multi-actor approach rubric that serves as a tool for both the preparation and evaluation of MAA proposals and to address the need for quality in assessing MAA in HEU projects.
- **Q&A document addressing questions related to the MAA.** This briefing document intends to provide basic answers to common questions posed during information or innovation brokerage events in the context of the MAA. At the same time, the Q&A document offers deeper insights for experienced users looking to engage further with the MAA funded by the HEU Framework Programme. The document will function as a living resource that will be regularly updated based on new questions, feedback, and further developments on the level of the funding programme.

The following subsections summarise the content and the potential role of the two briefing products, which are annexed to this D2.2 report.

4.1 Consideration of the MAA in Evaluation Summary Reports (ESR): from analysis to a quality rubric

One of the first joint activities by all PREMIERE partners consisted of the extraction of relevant statements regarding the assessment of the MAA in ESRs of project proposals. Consortium members looked for evaluation reports of

both successful and rejected MA proposals. This search resulted in 67 ESRs from Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe proposals, which related to PREMIERE's partner organisations. The statements were classified according to their quality, based on how well they reflected the definition of the MAA. Both qualitative and quantitative data were extracted during the exercise. As a result, this ESR-related policy briefing document (Annex I) includes...

- The methodology used for the analysis of the ESR statements, to allow it to be reproduced in the future with other sets of ESRs.
- The quantitative and qualitative summary of results.
- A selection of anonymised thirteen statements extracted from ESRs, offering examples of high-quality MAA evaluations, both positive and negative.
- Also eleven statements classified as unclear or of lower quality. These examples are of particular interest to both proposal writers and evaluators when they aim to improve the quality and precision of their MA-related paragraphs.

Moreover, the annexed document includes a rubric for evaluating MAA in proposals, designed as a tool for proposal drafters, evaluators, advisors, and trainers. This is based on the contents and other references. The rubric follows the typical format of these types of grids, which are commonly used in education at all levels. The rubric allows a scoring from the lowest to highest quality ratings of an MAA proposal relating to the different criteria of the MAA as defined by Horizon Europe guidance documents.

4.2 Detailed Question & Answer (Q&A) about the MAA

In the regular dialogue with PREMIERE policy and project officers, the need for a Q&A document emerged. It was discussed how far such a document could address the MAA-related questions that participants, in particular newcomers, commonly ask at information events about Horizon Europe funding. It was agreed that such a written contribution with answers to questions would be useful support for upcoming information days, brokerage and training events for Horizon MAA Calls. Hence, PREMIERE partners started an iterative and co-creative drafting process including a critical review of the first draft of a Q&A document before the inclusion in D2.2.

Since Q&A documents in general are expected to provide (only) basic guidance, this reduction was also foreseen for the preparation of the PREMIERE's Q&A document. The idea was to prepare a set of practice-oriented explanations that

serve as a resource, which offers basic answers for novices unfamiliar with MAA. At the same time, this document was expected to provide deeper insights for experienced users seeking helpful details associated with the MAA required in HEU projects.

During the co-creative process, the drafting team realised that the two objectives might contradict each other when the presentation of ‘deeper insights’ on how to implement the MAA in a proposal tends to emerge as good-practice recommendations or tips and tricks from experienced proposal developers. However, such good practice recommendations emerging from lessons learnt from various PREMIERE activities would need more space for methodological and context-specific justification. Since the strengths and characteristics of a common Q&A document are its conciseness and clarity, the paragraphs of well-elaborated good practice recommendations were taken out from the draft Q&A document again. They will now feed into other PREMIERE outputs such as the How-to guides prepared by the Task 3.3 team.

Annex II of D2.2 presents the results of this work aiming for concise and (legally) precise answers. The current version of the Q&A document is seen as a living document, which will be continuously updated. Future events in preparation for proposals addressing the Cluster-6-2025 Call will trigger new questions. The context of **the** Call Topics and the associated requirements may change, which will drive the development of adjusted or new answers.

5 NEXT STEPS

The two PREMIERE tasks focus on policy-related work in WP2: policy-making (macro-level governance in T2.1) and policy implementation (meso-level governance in T2.2) both related to the MAA. They are strongly interlinked. One insight from the ongoing work in WP2 was that a close alignment of the two tasks' progress and upcoming actions needs to be ensured. Both tasks address the enhancement of the MAA from a policy and implementation standpoint.

Towards the end of 2024, the WP2 team will process the results of the Focus Group process on challenges and solutions for programming and implementation of the MAA presented in D2.1. These also include aspects of drafting, MA training and education, evaluation, and granting of MA project proposals. The implementation of several of the solutions (presented in D2.1) is currently under review. The reflection and validation process associated with this will be part of the upcoming exploitation activities of PREMIERE.

Based on the work done and findings presented so far in D2.1 and D2.2, the forthcoming steps planned for PREMIERE's policy work include:

- Preparation of the next policy-level Focus Group. This event is expected to be held between November 2024 and early 2025. The focus will be on the quality evaluation of project proposals required to incorporate the MAA. Results from this Focus Group will feed into future policy briefing activities including policy briefs.
- Conceptualisation of the next policy-level Focus Group(s). Potential topics for the higher policy-level Focus Group, to be held in 2025, are currently under review. It could focus on Operational Groups' participation in Horizon Europe, the scope of the MAA beyond Cluster 6 and Horizon Europe, or the consideration of additional concepts such as Open Science and the RRI concepts and their alignment with the MA requirements.
- Support for the implementation of the MAA. The WP2 team will produce a short policy brief with key recommendations for MAA inclusion in project proposals. This policy brief will focus on enhancing the scoring of the MAA in the proposals. Only when the investigation and scorings of the reviewed proposals are consistent and rank proposals (not only but also) according to their MA methodologies, participatory impact pathways and an appropriate MA work plan concept, then proposal writers might change their habits and apply the MAA more thoroughly in future proposals than in the past. Such a strict and consequent assessment and scoring process is a way to prevent review processes from a superficial application and presentation of the MAA in the proposal, a phenomenon of 'multi-actor washing'. These reflections require further investigation.
- Preparation of an Evaluators' Guide. The WP2 team will work on a tool for evaluators, similar to an annotated template with examples from the ESR Rubric (as shown above).
- Trigger critical reflections about the enabling (policy) environment for MA projects in the next Framework Programme. The WP2 team will identify priorities aligned with the objectives of WP2 and policy priorities such as the development of recommendations for the preparation of the next Framework Programme FP10.
- Ensuring cross-fertilisation between PREMIEREWPs. WP2 outcomes will continue to feed into the preparation of output material in WP4 and WP5.
- Awareness of the policy-related work of the AKIS sister projects. PREMIERE's T1.3 ensures a continuous dialogue with the sister projects ATTRACTISS, EU-FarmBook, and ModernAKIS, which also engage with and develop policy briefs in the field of co-innovation. WP2 will remain aware of the ongoing work aiming for the enhancement of the MAA in these projects. Moreover, the collaboration with NCPs and their umbrella

projects Care4Bio and NCP4Mission will continue. These wide connections also bring opportunities at the governance level, including the discussion of the Focus Group results with the SCAR AKIS Strategic Working Group event, held in Bucharest, and the suggested presentation of the results to the NCPs.

Overall, the ongoing work in PREMIERE's WP2 with the policy engagement on the various European and national levels is well underway. Lessons learned from the ongoing work in PREMIERE's WPs show that Policy Briefing activities have to remain flexible. They need to adjust to the dynamics of policy-making and changing frameworks and processes. The finalisation of this Deliverable D2.2 provided the WP2 team with the opportunity to step back from the busy preparation of upcoming activities and instead, briefly reflect on the output prepared and insights gained so far from both the personal engagement with policy-makers and administrators as well as the thorough analysis of the powerful documents of the ESRs to remain focused on the further enhancement of the MAA.

ANNEXES

Annex I: Consideration of the multi-actor approach in Evaluation Summary Reports (ESR): from analysis to a quality rubric

Annex II: Question & Answer document on MAA

Policy briefing on ESRs

Consideration of the Multi-Actor Approach in Evaluation Summary Reports (ESR): From the analysis to a quality rubric

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1 INTRODUCTION

The Multi-Actor Approach (MAA) appeared for the first time and developed under Horizon 2020 during the 2nd mandate of the SCAR AKIS Strategic Working Group. Hence, it was further refined under the following mandates according to the discussions within the group and with the project coordinators invited to the meetings (EU SCAR AKIS 2019).

Within the Horizon 2020 programme (2014-2020), an estimated number of 184 Call Topics for proposals were flagged with a compulsory Eligibility Criterion to apply the MAA. The large majority of these were part of the Work Programme of the *Societal Challenge (SC) 9 - Food security, sustainable agriculture and forestry, marine and maritime and inland water research, and the bioeconomy*. In total, 20% of SC9 Call topics required the MAA. In Horizon Europe (2021-2027), the number of Call Topics with compulsory application of the MAA has notably increased. Already, 159 Topics were published with MAA requirement in the period 2021-2024. Moreover, their spectrum has increased, not only in the Horizon Global Challenge 6 (equivalent to SC9 in H2020) but also in Horizon Missions topics on ‘Soils’ and in ‘Oceans’, as well as in Horizon Partnerships and sister programmes like the Mediterranean PRIMA. Global Challenge 6 has reached 44% of Topics flagged MAA in 2021-2024. This is more than double compared to the previous programme.

Paragraphs defining the MAA have always been included. They were part of the official programme content in the general introduction to the Food, Agriculture and Forestry Challenge (SC9 in H2020, GC6 in HEurope) and presented as a reference for all persons involved in proposal and approved projects: applicants/beneficiaries, programme, project and DGs officers as well as the external evaluators involved in the review of Call Topics (Horizon Europe On-line manual includes a visual on all steps and actors involved¹). In this regard, the definition of the MAA has changed between the Horizon2020 and Horizon Europe Programme. The guidelines for the evaluation of the flagged MAA topic proposals have also experienced an evolution over the two programme periods. This official definition stands as the basic conceptual

¹ <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/funding-tenders-opportunities/display/OM/Online+Manual>

framework for all involved in the MAA, and it appears as a written text without an explicit means of quality evaluation.

This policy briefing document advocates for one specific tool, the **Multi-Actor Approach Rubric**, presented in the following section, to address this need of quality evaluation of the MAA.

Together with the MAA Rubric, the Evaluation Summary Report² (ESR) is the other relevant component of this document. The ESR is the final report of a proposal evaluation process. Each evaluating team has to agree on their jointly developed Evaluation Summary Report. The ESR of every Horizon Topic proposal must explain how far the applicants address the requested objectives, scope and additional requirements of the topic, which they are addressing and in which they need to incorporate the MAA. These documents allow applicants, European Commission Officers (DGs³ and REA⁴) and evaluators to reflect on the quality of a proposal according to the topic conditions (Figure 1). Therefore, the ESRs of MAA-flagged Topics represent a unique opportunity to assess and compare how the MAA has been viewed along the two Horizon programmes at the proposal stage.

Associated with document Ref. Ares(2022)4651869 - 24/06/2022

Proposal Evaluation Form		
	EUROPEAN COMMISSION Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON)	Evaluation Summary Report - Coordination and support actions
Call: Type of action: Proposal number: Proposal acronym: Duration (months): Proposal title: Activity:	HORIZON-CL6-2022-GOVERNANCE-01 HORIZON-CSA 101086531 PREMIERE 60 Preparing multi-actor projects in a co-creative way HORIZON-CL6-2022-GOVERNANCE-01-14	

Figure 1. Example of an ESR header (for the PREMIERE proposal)

The analysis behind this policy document used a large sample of ESRs (67) collected by PREMIERE partners, corresponding to Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe proposals to analyse descriptively, the evolution, trends, and

² See *Outcome of evaluation*: <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/funding-tenders-opportunities/display/OM/Evaluation+and+evaluation+results>.

³ https://commission.europa.eu/about-european-commission/departments-and-executive-agencies_en

⁴ https://rea.ec.europa.eu/index_en

opportunities for improvement in future MAA topic calls. The detailed methodology for this analysis is available in Annex 1.

The analysis of these 67 ESRs has allowed, on the one hand, to extract a useful sample of exemplary statements on MAA evaluation out of these ESRs, and on the other, to show the evolution of the quality in MAA evaluation, as shown on the final sections of this policy document.

Findings and recommendations of this Policy Document

- This policy document builds up on **a sample of 67 Evaluation Summary Reports (ESRs) of Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe proposals** connected to PREMIERE partners.
- A **new Rubric for MAA** proposal and evaluation processes is proposed as a common tool, for proposal writers, evaluators, advisers and trainers, to seize the quality of Topics and the proposals' MAA content based on the concepts of the definition and the MA requirements.
- **Version 1 of the rubric is presented** in this policy briefing document, envisioning future refinements of the tool that will be made available on the PREMIERE website and on Zenodo.
- A selection of **13 statements** were extracted **from ESRs, representing a sample of accurate quality statements** on MAA evaluation. Both positive (green) and negative (red) considerations were sampled.
- Secondly, this report presents a sample of eleven **ESR statements that are vague or of other unclear quality.**
- These curated samples of ESR statements are **a useful tool to complement the rubric**, especially at the evaluation level, but also as a reference for proposal writers, that can be visited as a reflection during any MAA writing or evaluation activity.
- Out of 67 ESRs with no statistical significance, **89% mention the MAA in the Excellence section** only, while 12% had still no explicit reference to the MAA although the Topics were labelled with the MAA, despite they may refer to it indirectly.

- The **quality of ESR statements has increased** between Horizon 2020 and the Horizon Europe Programme. Overall, 55% of ESR statements on MAA are of accurate or best quality in both Programmes.

2 A NEW RUBRIC FOR MULTI-ACTOR APPROACH PROPOSAL PREPARATION AND EVALUATION.

This policy briefing document merges the objectives of WP2 ‘Governance’ and WP3 ‘Projects’ of PREMIERE. It arises from the idea of identifying the best / worst characteristics of multi-actor proposals. One existing tool for this purpose is the use of **evaluation rubrics**.

A rubric is a learning and assessment tool that articulates the expectations for assignments and performance tasks by listing criteria, and for each criterion, describing levels of quality⁵ (Andrade, 2000; Arter & Chappuis, 2007).

Evaluation rubrics have been extensively used in teaching and learning contexts, and from there have evolved to assess the quality and performance of a wide range of processes and final products. The PREMIERE MAA rubric is a concept based on two rubrics in the literature in closer fields, one in Responsible Research and Innovation – RRI (Wickson and Carew 2014), and the other on networking agroecology demonstration farms (McGreevy et al 2014).

A few descriptors on the rubric *in italics*, were extracted from Wickson and Carew (2014).

Together with these above, we inspired the rubric contents from quality statements of ESRs (see section 4), as well as work derived from the previous Horizon 2020 project LIAISON⁶ and related papers.

The Rubric for MAA describes at five different quality levels (insufficient - routine – good – great - exemplary) the characteristics of nine different components or criteria of the multi-actor approach definition used in Cluster 6

⁵ From: <https://teaching.berkeley.edu/resources/assessment-and-evaluation/design-assessment/rubrics>, follow the link for further details on the rubric System.

⁶ <https://liaison2020.eu/>

of Horizon Europe; these rubric criteria include both the seven MAA requirements as well as some other connected aspects:

- Objectives and planning of the proposal target needs/problems/challenges of, and opportunities for, the (end-)users of the project results
- Key actors are well identified in the proposal, including interactive innovation groups, such as EIP-AGRI Operational Groups.
- There is a genuine and sufficient involvement of targeted actors, ensured and demonstrated over the whole course of the project.
- Involvement of key and targeted actors is ensured and demonstrated over the whole course of the project.
- Building blocks for the project proposal clearly come from science as well as from practice and tacit knowledge: it is a ‘co-creation’ process.
- Project results are ready for practice and broadly implemented.
- The project facilitates the multi-actor engagement process by making use of the most appropriate methods and expertise.
- The project provides an appropriate number of ‘practice abstracts’ in the common EIP-AGRI format, or other similarly effective solutions for topics outside EIP-AGRI / CAP-specific objectives.
- MAA is embedded throughout the proposal in all 3 Criteria, as highlighted by support persons of National Contact Points

Three other suggested criteria address the writing of ESRs and therefore, are targeting evaluators:

- Direct and indirect incorporation of the MAA in all sections of the proposal document and therefore also involvement of the different dimensions of the MAA across the ESR document.
- Precision of language in the ESR document, clarity of the language, relation to the MAA definition.
- MAA process analysis in the ESR.

We believe that the rubric could be useful for both:

- Potential **beneficiaries** of MAA call topics for their proposal development (training, designing, writing, revising), offered by advisors like **NCPs** or **private consultants**.
- **Evaluators** of MAA proposals and responsible **EC officers**. With a concluding section on the rubric specially targeted for them.
- **Policy Officers drafting** MAA proposals who can use the rubric for a stronger alignment of Topic texts with the MA setting of the particular research question, sector or societal challenge.
- **Advisors and trainers** in proposal preparation, e. g. for InfoDays, dedicated training, and consultancy for coordinators.

The Rubric is also available as an independent appendix. This is version 1 of the Rubric. It might further develop to be refined if the approach is seen as a valuable tool by the users.

Any feedback from potential users will contribute to the refinement undertaken by the PREMIERE team.

CRITERIA TO BE CONSIDERED WHEN WRITING / EVALUATING MULTI-ACTOR APPROACH PROPOSALS

Criteria		Exemplary / 5	Great / 4	Good / 2	Routine / 1	Insufficient/0
		Best of best means:	Best means:	Correct means:	Minimum means:	Below threshold
1	<p>Objectives and planning of the proposal target needs/problems/challenges of, and opportunities for, the (end-)users of the project results</p>	<p>Takes a large-scale approach to complex challenges/opportunities at the multi-actor level.</p> <p>Clearly shows a co-creative ongoing analysis (started at proposal preparation stage or before) with users involved, to solve multiple challenges simultaneously (wicked solutions = related to wicked problems, that are difficult to solve because it is complex and contradictory; in need of very diverse groups of people to change their mindset).</p>	<p>Addresses a significant need for high multi-actor value.</p> <p>A co-creative process of connection between objectives and planning of the proposal and the users of the project is presented specifying the needs, problems, challenges and opportunities, and how these will be jointly co-created to deliver a successful solution.</p>	<p>The focus of the proposal is partial, marginal or has a limited multi-actor value.</p> <p>There is a clear connection between objectives and planning of the proposal and the users of the project results specifying the needs, problems, challenges and opportunities addressed toward a solution or partial solution.</p>	<p>The focus of the proposal is unclear or it responds to an interest of a limited group of actors.</p> <p>Needs/problems/challenges of and opportunities for the (end-)users of the project results are partially or briefly addressed creating limited and or decontextualized knowledge.</p>	<p>There is no focus for the proposal or it is clearly not well formulated.</p> <p>Needs/problems / challenges of and opportunities for the (end-)users of the project results are insufficiently or incorrectly addressed in the objectives and planning of the proposal</p>
2	<p>Key actors are well identified in the proposal, including interactive innovation groups, such as EIP-AGRI Operational Groups.</p>	<p>The proposal includes a very well-balanced, well-developed and clearly described composition of actors, and all partners have a delineated and valid role in the project.</p> <p>It encompasses a wide range of actors, balanced at geographical as well as social, gender, sectoral and at 4-helix levels. Interactive innovation groups in the AKIS ecosystem and beyond,</p>	<p>The proposal includes a thorough and well-explained selection of actors to be involved at different levels. All key groups are represented, with consideration to geographical balance, including interactive innovation groups in the AKIS ecosystem.</p>	<p>The proposal identifies and includes major actor types but not a detailed and well-explained selection of actors to be involved at different levels. Key groups, geographical balance and interactive innovation groups in the AKIS ecosystem are discussed, but it is unclear if the proposal covers them adequately.</p>	<p>The proposal outlines several actors with limited reasoning for the selection. Key groups are not identified in detail making it difficult to value their representativeness. No consideration of geographical balance or any other criteria, interactive innovation groups in the AKIS ecosystem were not considered or poorly analysed.</p>	<p>Insufficient detail was provided on the number and type of actors.</p>

CITERIA TO BE CONSIDERED WHEN WRITING / EVALUATING MULTI-ACTOR APPROACH PROPOSALS

Criteria		Exemplary / 5	Great / 4	Good / 2	Routine / 1	Insufficient/0
		Best of best means:	Best means:	Correct means:	Minimum means:	Below threshold
		including OG where relevant, have a structural role in the actors' framework of the proposal.				
3	<p>There is a genuine and sufficient involvement of targeted actors, ensured and demonstrated over the whole course of the project.</p>	<p><i>Openly and actively seeking ongoing critical input, feedback and feedback from a range of stakeholders. Harder-to-reach and specific knowledge groups are part of the consortium in well-defined roles. Encouraging and rewarding transformative mutual learning. Employing an evolving integrative method and consciously employing a transdisciplinary (TD) process (e.g. Pennington et al 2013).</i></p>	<p><i>Inviting, incorporating and integrating stakeholder views at various points along the research and innovation process. Harder-to-reach and specific knowledge groups are well-identified and partly engaged in the proposal. Actively seeking dialogic interaction with stakeholders and open to mutual learning. Encompassing a wide range of methods (including, but not only, co-creation, co-implementation. co-evaluation) and adopting an interdisciplinary process.</i></p>	<p><i>Limited stages of the research and innovation process are open for stakeholder engagement. The tendency toward one-way forms of communication (e.g. validation only) with stakeholders but open to some interaction. Involving some level of methodological diversity and multidisciplinary practice. Hard to reach and specific knowledge groups somewhat considered.</i></p>	<p>No involvement (or insufficient evidence of) of targeted actors in the development of the project idea.</p> <p>Limited involvement of targeted actors in the research and innovation process which may be one-way and with limited methodological and disciplinary diversity. Lack of a comprehensive bottom-up approach with targeted actors.</p>	<p>Concept and methodology do poorly show how practitioners and their organisations are targeted from the planning to the execution of the project work.</p>

CRITERIA TO BE CONSIDERED WHEN WRITING / EVALUATING MULTI-ACTOR APPROACH PROPOSALS

Criteria		Exemplary / 5	Great / 4	Good / 2	Routine / 1	Insufficient/0
		Best of best means:	Best means:	Correct means:	Minimum means:	Below threshold
4	<p>Research and innovation processes open to dialogue and responsive to actors and stakeholders</p>	<p><i>Structured, purposeful periodic analytical review of underlying values, assumptions and choices. Actively seeking critical feedback from a wide group of sources and actors, including networking structures among dispersed communities. Evidence of potential to adapt at a range of points in response to in-train reflective practice and external review/input/feedback. Active use of complementary forms of knowledge, practitioners' practical and local knowledge and/or entrepreneurial skills to develop solutions.</i></p>	<p><i>Occasional use of structured processes for reflecting on underlying values, assumptions and choices. Actively seeking critical feedback from select sources and actors. Clear indications of a capacity to adapt in response to reflective practice and external feedback. The proposal shows signs of some capacity to use practical and local knowledge from practitioners.</i></p>	<p><i>Informal, one-off or ad hoc process for considering underlying values, assumptions and choices. Accepting critical feedback when offered. Stated willingness to accept change in response to internal reflective practice or external review and critique.</i></p>	<p><i>No process for facilitating reflective practice. No critique is sought. No evidence of potential for change in response to criticism / unsolicited feedback.</i></p>	<p>Practitioners and (end) users are mainly involved as a study-object. Dialogue is mostly one-way.</p>

CRITERIA TO BE CONSIDERED WHEN WRITING / EVALUATING MULTI-ACTOR APPROACH PROPOSALS

Criteria		Exemplary / 5	Great / 4	Good / 2	Routine / 1	Insufficient/0
		Best of best means:	Best means:	Correct means:	Minimum means:	Below threshold
5	Building blocks for the project proposal come from science as well as from practice and tacit knowledge: it is a 'co-creation' process	The project proposal is co-designed between all actors involved and deeply embedded in a co-creative work process clearly blending science and practice knowledge/techniques in a shared learning-by-doing process. Bottom-up and top-down initiatives embedded in the project process will ensure a bridging process between all actors. The creation of 'co-ownership' of results for (end-) users and practitioners is high-quality and its feasibility is demonstrated via knowledge exchange activities.	The project proposal is based on some dialogue and contribution by the actors involved and shows means and strategies for co-creative work process that shall ensure science and practice collaboration. Bottom-up and top-down initiatives are considered. Knowledge exchange activities are planned at a scale which should facilitate 'co-ownership' of results for (end-) users and practitioners.	The project proposal plans to carry out occasional actions promoting dialogue and contribution towards co-creation by actors involved, without a consistent and continued strategy for science and practice collaboration throughout the project. Bottom-up and top-down initiatives are considered but not aligned to ensure science-practice exchange.	The proposal has a classical research for practice transfer approach. Co-creative science and practice partnerships are largely absent or, if mentioned, the work process follows a non-co-creative approach. Little to no use of practitioners and traditional knowledge was seen.	The co-creation principle is not adequately addressed. Knowledge exchange and cross-fertilisation of skills is not demonstrated
6	Project results are ready for practice and broadly implemented	Ensure wide dissemination of results at practice and external levels, by actively overcoming language and geographical barriers, and actively using synergies between projects at the European scale, communities of practice and easy-to-access outputs in general. Project results planned for use	Clear dissemination of results at practice and external level, with some identified limitations with contingency plans. Active plans to make broad use of exchange opportunities with farmers, visitors and at training. Project results planned for use beyond the project duration.	Dissemination of results at the practice and external level is considered in general terms with no clear means to reach out to practitioners. Limited plans to make use of exchange opportunities with farmers, visitors and at training. General but limited plans to use results	Basic and classical means of dissemination of results at practice and external level, correction measures not identified. Target groups identified without a clear outreach strategy. Use of project results beyond the project duration with little credibility.	Project results dissemination is limited to the project digital media or collateral activities planned by some partners. Practice level not specifically addressed. Specific target groups not identified.

CRITERIA TO BE CONSIDERED WHEN WRITING / EVALUATING MULTI-ACTOR APPROACH PROPOSALS

Criteria		Exemplary / 5	Great / 4	Good / 2	Routine / 1	Insufficient/0
		Best of best means:	Best means:	Correct means:	Minimum means:	Below threshold
		beyond the project duration.		beyond the project duration.		
7	The project facilitates the multi-actor engagement process by making use of the most appropriate methods and expertise	MAA is reframed in innovative directions beyond current practice, with new ideas being pursued through appropriate methods. Resources are carefully considered and allocated to efficiently achieve maximum use and impact of the MAA. Stakeholder engagement consideration is given to preconditions, processes and products.	New methods for MAA are being developed according to new ideas within an established problem framing. The use of resources is explicitly justified by the MAA. Stakeholder engagement consideration is given to processes and products.	New ideas are being pursued through established MAA methods within an accepted problem framing. Resources are too limited, or inefficiently employed for MAA. Stakeholder engagement consideration is given to envisaged products.	Problem framing, ideas and methods fall within established paradigms of the MAA. Extensive resources (e.g. time, money, personnel, etc.) are dedicated to work with minimal significance or potential impact on MAA. No consideration is given to the stakeholder engagement of operating preconditions, research and innovation process or envisaged products	Methods are very general, basically with unidirectional participation in MAA. No resources are planned for MAA. The project preconditions, processes and products are totally disconnected from the stakeholders it targets.
8	The project provides an appropriate number of 'practice abstracts' in the common EIP-AGRI format, or other similarly effective solutions for topics outside	Practice abstracts are planned, and quantified in number and expected dissemination. Different abstract dissemination tools, events and activities are identified, including open-source databases targeting different stakeholder types like Zenodo, CAP network, or	Practice abstracts are clearly described and considered means of dissemination. MAA is part of the abstract development. The content of the practice abstracts is designed for clarity and visual use.	Practice abstracts are described in some detail and are part of the general project dissemination plans. No further concretion is provided.	The proposal mentions practice abstracts without further detail on their development and dissemination.	The proposal misses to mention practice abstracts.

CRITERIA TO BE CONSIDERED WHEN WRITING / EVALUATING MULTI-ACTOR APPROACH PROPOSALS

Criteria		Exemplary / 5	Great / 4	Good / 2	Routine / 1	Insufficient/0
		Best of best means:	Best means:	Correct means:	Minimum means:	Below threshold
	EIP-AGRI / CAP-specific objectives.	FarmBook. Practice abstracts have been developed within an MAA. The content of the practice abstracts has been pre-tested for practitioners usability and it is clear and visual.				
9	MAA is embedded throughout the Horizon proposal in all 3 sections (Excellence, Impact, Implementation)	The MAA is transversal in the project proposal and it is clearly highlighted in all 3 sections and in those sections and aspects of the proposal where it is relevant. Partner descriptions in Part A address their MAA role as well. The proposal budget is according to its MAA.	The MAA is evident throughout the project proposal and all 3 sections refer to it.	MAA is well described in the Excellence section, and mentioned in a few other points of the proposal.	MAA is part of the proposal but only Implementation makes it explicit.	MAA is only implicit in Excellence or Implementation, without a clear development in the proposal.

SPECIFIC CRITERIA FOR ESR WRITING (evaluation process)

Criteria	Exemplary / 5	Great / 4	Good / 2	Routine / 1	Insufficient/0
	Best of best means:	Best means:	Correct means:	Minimum means:	Below threshold
MAA across ESR	All 3 evaluation sections mention MAA. Excellence focuses on the main evaluation of the MAA of the proposal, while the Impact and Implementation ESR sections consider the MAA about the criteria analysed on each (e.g. budget and WP distribution between the different actors, or specific impact and dissemination targets for multi-actor subgroups.)	Excellence and Implementation sections mention MAA in detail with quality statements and some analysis of the quality of MAA in the proposed implementation.	The Excellence section mentions MAA in detail and Implementation briefly.	Only excellence mentions MAA.	MAA not mentioned in the ESR.
Precision of Language (section 4 guidance for evaluators)	Clear and comprehensive language, covering all relevant aspects of the MAA definition. Statements resembling best quality in PREMIERE ESR analysis paper. Both positive and negative MAA statements with detail and quality.	Clear and comprehensive language, based on the MAA definition. Statements on MAA clearly show the evaluators' qualifications.	Language is partly based on the MAA definition but uses other unprecise terms. Statements on MAA somewhat show the evaluators' qualifications but with imprecision or insufficient connection to the MAA definition.	MAA included in the ESR only using unclear and or unprecise terms. ESR statements with insufficient connection to the MAA definition.	MAA is not mentioned in the ESR.
MA Process	The MA process from proposal preparation to implementation and post-execution is well analysed and evaluated in terms of process, actors, methodology and innovation networking. All 9 rubric criteria for the proposal preparation above are evident in the ESR no matter the extent of limitations.	The MA process from proposal preparation to implementation and post-execution is analysed. Most of all 9 criteria of the rubric for proposal preparation above are evident in the ESR.	The MA process from proposal preparation to implementation and post-execution is partially analysed. Some of the 9 criteria of the rubric for proposal preparation above are not considered.	The MA process is poorly and partially considered in the evaluation. Some key aspects are not mentioned. Several of the 9 criteria of the rubric for proposal preparation above are not considered.	MAA is not mentioned in the ESR.

3 SELECTION OF ESR STATEMENTS ON THE MULTI-ACTOR APPROACH

The second practical contribution of this policy briefing document is a selection of statements on actual ESRs related to the MAA. This selection of statements can help better focus the preparation of multi-actor proposals and evaluators of future proposals.

The text in *italics* is literal to that of the ESR, excluding any information that could disclose the evaluated proposal. Using brackets (...) the proposal-specific part of the selected statement is excluded. Each statement is followed by the topic type, noted in brackets (RIA, IA, or CSA/TN) and the corresponding Framework Programme (H2020 or HEU). The coloured parts of the statements, emphasised *in green*, reflect texts of accurate quality describing *positive aspects* related to the MAA requirement in this proposal while those *in red* represent concerns of the review team in the proposal. The phrasing of these shortcomings is also part of an accurate quality ESR but resulted in a lowered score. Finally, the *Asterisk indicates when we add a comment after the statement in *italics*.

Selection of accurate good-quality ESR statements on MAA

The following statements represent positive evaluation results associated with the application of the MAA:

1. *There is a strong emphasis on user-focused, co-creative work, seeking to explore and find ways to strengthen application of the Multi-Actor Approach (MAA). (...) The proposal incorporates a comprehensive range of methods to facilitate a multi-actor engagement process, e.g., stakeholder panels, collection of experiences, brokerage events, and joint development and testing of tools via co-design workshops. There is also a strong emphasis on iterative stakeholder dialogue supporting all stakeholders' efforts (including harder to reach groups) to improve the take-up of the MAA in proposals. (CSA HEU)*
2. *Interdisciplinary approach and exchange of stakeholders' knowledge (multi-actor approach) is one of the strongest points of this proposal. There is an excellent description of the three major roles that interaction between stakeholders and inter-transfer of their knowledge plays. The focus is clearly embedded in the different work packages (WP) aiming to get the maximum*

out of the different stakeholders. The *research integrating the social aspects of knowledge and innovation uptake by farmers* is a new approach, which is very positive. However, the active contributions from farmers mainly rely on interviews and surveys and on a limited number of very small groups. (RIA H2020)

3. *The composition of the research consortium involving not only academic partners, but also practitioners and policy makers in all research stages, including analytical work and analysis, makes a model multi-actor approach. The multi-actor approach is used for the creation of bottom-up and top-down initiatives.* (RIA H2020) *This statement is in criterion 2 (Impact) of an ESR that has an unclear quality statement in criterion 1.
4. *The use of top-down and bottom-up approaches in combination with a multi-actor approach is very suitable to deliver useful, applicable and appealing end-user material for farmers. The very clear and strong bottom-up focus is a clear strength. (...) The multi-actor approach will be implemented with a very well-balanced composition of the consortium. Additionally, all types of stakeholders will be actively involved in the project.* (CSA HEU)
5. *Multi-actor approach is very well demonstrated both theoretically (AKIS concept, systemic analysis, transformative learning, participative approach) and in practice, involving an organic farming sector via a partner, and individual farmers like xxx in international hackathons.* (c.43 IA HEU)
*This is an example of a relatively short but clear positive statement.
6. *The Multi-Actor Approach is very well incorporated in the different project phases, spanning the entire spectrum of co-creation, co-implementation and co-evaluation of the project activities and the different types of actors involved. End-users (rural communities and actors) and community stakeholders are explicitly indicated in the proposal as key actors for project implementation and receptors of generated solutions.* (CSA HEU).
7. *The resources assigned to WPs are in line with their tasks, objectives and deliverables. For example, the total average workload is well aligned with the multi-actor, interactive and novel characteristics of the proposal.* (H2020 RIA).

*One of only two statements in the Implementation section with the high-quality value of analysing workload in the consortium versus the MAA.

8. *The consortium brings together the relevant expertise needed to carry out the activities. In addition, the representation of practitioner-related organisations is quite significant and is a strength. The consortium presents a very well-balanced composition and all partners have a valid role in the project. Most of the partners have very relevant experience and interest in multi-actor approaches and interlinking innovation with implementation in practice, which is a strength. In addition, all partners have relevant expertise of [the topic] management in European Research & Development and Coordination and Support Actions-projects, which is also a strength. (CSA HEU)*

*Second statement that we identified in the Implementation section.

The following statements reflect **negative aspects** of the proposal on MAA in ESRs. They show aspects that evaluators consider when they agreed on a **low MAA qualification**. Two statements are mixed with **positive statements**, which are highlighted in **green** again).

9. *The multi-actor approach is well integrated at the core of the methodology. Research co-design and knowledge co-creation will happen in the multi-scale nested case study approach (from field to farm, to biophysical and socio-economically defined regions to broader food systems), mobilizing existing multi-actor communities of practice while involving farmers in farm-level research. Other actors and stakeholders, such as entrepreneurs from different fields of interest will also be adequately considered. However, the composition of each multi-actor community of practice remains unclear for each selected region, with insufficient detail provided on the number and type of actors, and the role of farmers in each of them. This is a shortcoming. (RIA HEU).*

10. *The strong multi-actor and multi-sectoral approach is interdisciplinary, encompasses a wide range of actors and locations and it is generally well developed and clearly described, however a shortcoming is that the proposal does not sufficiently demonstrate how it will engage with smaller farms, the food services sector and consumers. Social sciences and humanities are insufficiently addressed and lack clear outputs, for example the social aspect of sustainability has a limited focus on localized production and the engagement of local communities. (IA H2020).*

*The SSH statement is negative too but not focused on MAA, thus we do not highlight it.

11. *It is a significant weakness that the methodology does not make sufficient provision for wide, multi-actor and representative inclusion, engagement or participation of rural dwellers and stakeholders as explicitly expected in the topic. (CSA H2020).*

*This is the first example of a Weakness statement in our sample, which disqualifies the proposal.

12. *The multi-actor approach is in general appropriately applied. The use of participatory decision and stakeholder engagement support tools is addressed in line with the requirements of the call. However, the methodology fails to design a comprehensive bottom-up approach that will actively involve rural dwellers and farmers throughout the project. This is a shortcoming. (CSA H2020)*

13. *The concept and methodology do poorly show how farmers and farmers' organisations are targeted from the planning to the execution of the project work which is a shortcoming. Overall, the project does not sufficiently show active involvement of end-users in all phases as participatory activities are foreseen for validation only. Thus, the co-creation principle is not adequately addressed. To conclude, the multi-actor approach is not sufficiently demonstrated in the concept and methodology of the project, which is a weakness. (CSA H2020).*

*This is the second example of a Weakness statement in our sample, which disqualifies the proposal.

Selection of lacking clarity about the MAA in the ESR statements

*In this selection we are not highlighting any text because the wording will not serve as positive examples for potential future use in ESR statements.

14. *The multi-actor approach is adequate, with a further number of additional end user organizations, e.g. farmer groups and advisors, being considered during the development and execution of the activities. (TN, H2020)*

15. *The proposal fulfils all the requirements of multi-actor approach (MAA) using innovation networks to connect research and practice actors at national and European level. (TN HEU).*

16. *The inter-disciplinary multi-actor approach is convincing and covers well a scientist-stakeholder-industry triangle. (RIA HEU)*

17. *The methodology framework affiliates with the multi actor approach. (RIA H2020) *This statement is in criterion 1 of an ESR that has a high-quality statement in criterion 2.*
18. *It will also actively involve and engage with a range of actors (in line with the multi-actor approach) and connect the relevant economies to provide new business models in the agri-food market including sustainability. (RIA H2020)*
19. *The Multi-Actor Approach (MAA) is excellently addressed, scientists, innovation trainers, farm advisory services and government are involved throughout. (RIA HEU)*
20. *The multi-actor approach is described in general terms, but it has been insufficiently planned, as the identification of key stakeholders is planned to occur after its start. This is a shortcoming. (RIA HEU).*
21. *The proposal has a good multi-actor approach which builds on the existing Innovation Networks with large farmer representation as well as local operational groups, SMEs, advisory and extension services, EIP service technicians and policymakers. (TN H2020)*
22. *The multi-actor approach is integrated into the objectives. However there is a lack of detail regarding end-user involvement, this is a minor shortcoming. (RIA H2020)*
23. *The concept and the methodological approach rest on a multi-actor approach, and the proposal pays special attention to farming, women, young people and migrants, which is also positive. (RIA-stage-2 H2020)*
24. *The multi actor approach is very well presented with clearly involvement of actors at different levels. (IA H2020)*
25. *The proposal integrates in a coherent way the end-users, farmers, industry and other stakeholders, thereby providing a well-balanced multiactor approach. (IA H2020)*

4 QUANTITATIVE RESULTS OF THE ESR ANALYSIS

Sections 4 and 5 of this report present a grouped analysis of all ESRs considered in this document. We estimate that our sample of 67 ESRs included approximately 23% of the 184 Topics with MAA requirements published in the period 2014-2022 (H2020). In addition, 76 MAA Topics were selected for funding for the 2021-22 period of Horizon Europe (HEU). The actual percentage may be somewhat smaller because different ESRs in the sample may share the same Call Topic (as unknown in a confidential sample). Six ESRs correspond to Topics with 1st and 2nd evaluation stages. These were counted only once for each proposal.

As shown in Table 1, the sample ranges even between the two Framework Programmes with a majority of Research and Innovation Action (RIA) Topics, followed by CSA proposals. These reflect the pattern of percentages in Horizon MAA Topics. Overall, 40% of ESRs analysed represent successful proposals, which were selected for funding while 60% were rejected, thus including diversity in the sample in terms of positive and negative evaluations.

The implementation of the MAA is a compulsory evaluation item for Section 1-Excellence, according to the Horizon Evaluators Grid. It is optional for the other two Sections (2-Impact and 3-Implementation). This is reflected in the following results where 90% of ESRs mention MAA only in one section (Excellence at large). It is notorious that 12% (8) of the ESR sample had no explicit reference to MAA on Topics although labelled as MAA. However, the ESRs might refer to it indirectly (Table 2).

Table 1: Descriptive characteristics of the ESR sample

Programme period	Sample (n=67)	Percentage
HEU	34	51%
H2020	33	49%

Type of project	Sample (n=67)	Percentage	Type per programme period (sample number)	
			H2020	HEU
RIA	36	55%	15	21
IA	8	12%	6	2
CSA	23	34%	12	11
Thematic Network (TN)	5	7%		
Other	18	27%		

Funding status	Sample (n=67)	Percentage
Yes	27	40%
No	40	60%

Table 2: MAA references addressing 1, 2 or 3 evaluation sections

	MAA addressed directly in all three Sections	MAA addressed directly in two Sections	MAA is directly addressed in only one Section (mostly Excellence)
Sample (n=67)	3	3	53
% Y/D	5%	5%	90%
TOTAL Y/D	59	88%	
TOTAL N/D	8	12%	

5 QUALITATIVE RESULTS OF THE ESR ANALYSIS

This quality analysis is based solely on ESR statements that mention explicitly the MAA. The statements referring indirectly to MAA have not been analysed as their qualification tends to be subjective. Statements have been qualified as:

- Good quality: high-quality statements in terms of clarity and comprehensiveness.
- YES or NO: quality assessment on whether their quality is above or below an acceptable threshold. NO is often given because the statement(s) do not reflect sufficiently clearly the whole MAA concept as defined in the Horizon programmes. YES means that the MAA is addressed often short but within acceptable limits.
- N/A: Not applicable indicates that the ESR does not mention explicitly the MAA. In terms of sample evaluation ESRs of this category sum to the imprecise quality category.

The qualification exercise has been performed by a member of PREMIERE consortium with evaluation experience in H2020 and HEU. All ESRs were qualified by the same person.

Table 3: Quantification of quality of ESR statements in MAA across the sample

Project Type	Are the statements on MAA of accurate quality?				TOTAL
	BEST	YES (accurate)	NO (unclear)	N/A	
H2020					
RIA	1	6	5	3	15
IA	1	1	2	2	6
CSA (incl TN)	0	5	6	1	12
TOTAL	2	12	13	6	33
	6%	36%	39%	18%	
HEU					
RIA	2	10	7	2	21
IA	0	1	1	0	2
CSA (incl TN)	2	8	1	0	11
TOTAL	4	19	9	2	34
	12%	56%	26%	6%	
GLOBAL TOTAL					
	6	31	21	8	
	9%	46%	33%	12%	

As shown in Table 3 and Figure 2, the quality of ESR statements has increased between programmes (red cells/orange bars in H2020 vs. green cells/blue bars in HEU). Comparing the two Programme periods, more than half (55%) of ESR statements on MAA are of accurate or very good quality (orange cells in Table 3, with this percentage increasing to 68% in HEU).

Figure 2. Number of ESRs according to quality of MAA statements.

6 REFERENCES

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All partner organisations of the PREMIERE project have facilitated ESR statements on a multi-actor approach. This effort resulted in an excellent set of data for this analysis. The template for data collection of ESR statements on multi-actor is available at request to jordi@highclere-consulting.com.

ANNEX. METHODOLOGY OF THE ESR ANALYSIS INCLUDING INSTRUCTIONS FOR REPLICATION

The 15 partner organisations of PREMIERE jointly collected and systematized reference data of a total of 67 ESRs including:

- Programme (Horizon 2020 or Horizon Europe),
- Topic type (RIA, IA, CSA, and Thematic Network, as a specific kind of CSA),
- Indication of success of the proposal under evaluation,
- Direct (explicitly mentioning MAA) and indirect (related to but not mentioning MAA), statements included in the ESR, differentiated per each of the evaluation criteria (Excellence, Impact, Implementation),
- Optional value comments by the person filling in the data.

All this information was collected in a single confidential dataset to respect the data protection of each ESR provider. Moreover, some statements were slightly modified to ensure confidentiality.

The analysis of the dataset includes:

- Descriptive quantification of the ESRs compiled (programme, topic type, success, stage, etc.).
- Proportion of Direct and Indirect references to MAA in ESRs per each of the three evaluation criteria.
- Quality of the MAA evaluations based on the MAA guidelines for evaluators. We compared each individual statement to the evaluation guidelines and official definition and classified these as low – accurate – best quality.
- Trends and evolution of ESR content on MAA between programmes and in relation to the evolution of MAA definition.
- A selection of outstanding first quality ESR statements showing: i) Absolute clarity of the ESR text on MAA, in relation to guidance to evaluators; ii) Where evaluators have identified that MAA is deeply embedded in the whole proposal.

The final goal is to contribute to the recommendations on improving the application of and wider participation in the MAA.

How to use the PREMIERE ESR analysis model

The approach for the ESR analysis was developed and tested by the PREMIERE team taking into account that such an analysis of ESR statements could be also useful for NCPs (National Contact Points) and agencies alike. These support organisation could use the PREMIERE approach to compile and analyse sets of ESRs from their perspective in order to deliver advice to their national targets groups. in the same way we present here. We can facilitate the template database used for this analysis⁷, to repeat and extend it to other sets of ESRs.

The steps we followed for this analysis are:

1. Select ESRs of project proposals in topics labelled for MAA.
2. Revise all the ESR to search for the keyword “multi-actor approach” and save the full sentence or paragraph on the database under the corresponding criteria (excellence, impact, implementation), registering also all other common data (programme, type of project, funding success). Repeat this operation with as many statements and ESRs you have.
3. We also compiled statements with an indirect reference to multi-actor, but we did not use them in this analysis as it represented a large increase of data which we considered that could bring too much subjectivity to the analysis.
4. Next with a yes/no (1/0) indication we registered all ESRs on whether MAA appeared as a keyword in each of the three sections⁸.
5. The third step, regardless of the number of statements on MAA in one or more sections, is to classify the quality of ESR consideration of the MAA as: best quality (excellence), accurate or unclear. This was based on comparing the statements with the MAA definition of Horizon 2020 /

⁷ See indications at the end of this paper.

⁸ The indication to evaluators is to evaluate MAA under the excellence criteria, and our results reflect that at large. However, we considered that the term MAA can optionally be used in all criteria as part of other aspects evaluated.

Horizon Europe programmes. Here there is a degree of subjectivity that we limited by the same person qualifying all ESRs.

6. In parallel to step 3 above, we also identified the best (accurate) and lesser quality (unclear) MAA statements in all our samples, which after filtering are the last section of this report.
7. The last step was to calculate the summary data shown at the bottom of the template, which allowed us to obtain the quantitative results shown next.

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Questions and Answers for the Horizon Europe Multi-Actor Eligibility Condition

Annex II of Deliverable D2.2 - Policy briefings for policymakers for the implementation of the Multi-Actor Approach

Working document, October 2024

PREMIERE teams involved in the preparation:
METK, CREA, HCC, HNEE

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List of Abbreviations

CAP – Common Agricultural Policy

CSA – Coordination and Support action

CORDIS – Community Research and Development Information Service

DG – Directorate General of the European Commission

EC – European Commission

EIP-AGRI – European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability

ESR – The Evaluation Summary Report

HEU – Horizon Europe

IA – Innovation Action

IPR – Intellectual Property Rights

LLA – Living Lab Approach

MAA – Multi-Actor Approach

NCP – National Contact Point

OG – Operational Group

PA – Practice Abstract

REA – European Research Executive Agency

RIA – Research and Innovation Action

TN – Thematic Networks (special type of CSA)

About this briefing document

In the regular dialogue with PREMIERE policy and project officers, the need for a Q&A document emerged in the winter of 2023/2024. It was discussed how far such a document could address the MAA-related questions that participants - in particular newcomers - commonly ask at information events about Horizon Europe funding. It was agreed that such a written contribution with answers to common questions could be useful support for upcoming information days, brokerage and training events as well as individual website visitors seeking information for the MAA.

Since Q&A documents or website sections in general are expected to provide (only) basic guidance, this reduction was also foreseen for the preparation of the PREMIERE's Q&A document. The strengths and characteristics of a common Q&A document are its conciseness and clarity. For that reason, the authoring team decided to avoid a presentation of good practice recommendations because tips and tricks from lessons learnt are always context or Call-specific results that require explanation or justification. Often, explanations for the selection of certain facts or stories are diverse or even complex. Therefore, such longer explanations contradict the purpose of a simplified presentation of distinct answers to a concise question in the Q&A document. Good practices and tips and tricks for MA proposal writing will be part of the PREMIERE How-to-guides (output of WP3).

This is a living document. The results prepared so far will feed into discussions and documents, which are ongoing and will continue to evolve. In this sense, the following paragraphs represent work in progress that will be further refined and published on the PREMIERE website for dissemination and exploitation.

The document has four sections, which focus on questions about 1) the MAA in general, 2) the role of EIP-AGRI Operational Groups, 3) the financial aspects of actor and stakeholder involvement, and 4) the evaluation of multi-actor project proposals.

Questions focusing on understanding the multi-actor approach (MAA) and the Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HEU)

1 How to identify whether the multi-actor approach is required for a Horizon Europe project proposal?

The requirement for applying the multi-actor approach in a specific Horizon Europe Call is clearly stated in the Work Programme as an Eligibility condition listed under the Specific conditions of the call. Additional details may be included in the call text under the Expected Outcome and/or Scope.

2 What are the compulsory requirements for a multi-actor Horizon Europe project proposal?

The most recent definition and specific requirements of the multi-actor approach as applied in Horizon Europe can be found in the Introduction to the current versions of a) the Horizon Europe Cluster 6 (Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment) Work Programme and b) the Soil Deal for Europe Mission in the Horizon Europe Missions and Cross-cutting Activities Work Programme.

In general terms, multi-actor project proposals must ensure the “genuine and sufficient involvement of a targeted array of actors, which serves the objectives of the topic”. A comprehensive list of potential actors is included in the Work Programme. Furthermore, “The genuine and sufficient involvement of such actors should take place all over the whole course of the project: from participation in the development of the project idea, planning and experiments to implementation, communication and dissemination of results and to a possible demonstration phase.”

Following the current version of the Specific requirements for multi-actor projects in the Horizon Europe Cluster 6 Work Programme, a multi-actor

project proposal must include the following seven (7) elements that demonstrate HOW:

- the proposed objectives and planning are targeting the needs/problems/challenges of and opportunities for the (end-) users of the project results;
- the description of the project concept and in particular the composition of the consortium reflects a balanced choice of relevant key actors who have complementary types of knowledge (scientific, practical, etc.), and must ensure that project results which should be ready for practice are broadly implemented;
- the project intends to use existing practices and tacit knowledge. This should be illustrated in the proposal with a *sufficient* number of high-quality knowledge exchange activities outlining the precise and active roles of the different non-scientific actors in the work. The cross-fertilisation of skills, competencies and ideas between actors should generate innovative findings and solutions that are more likely to be applied on a wide scale;
- the project will facilitate the multi-actor engagement process by making use of the most appropriate methods and expertise;
- the project will complement existing research and best practices (its added value);
- the project will result in practical and ready-to-use knowledge, approaches, tools or products, that are easily understandable and freely accessible;
- these outputs ready for practice will feed into the existing dissemination channels most consulted by the (end-)users of the project results at the national/regional level.

In addition, multi-actor Horizon Europe projects must produce ‘practice abstracts’ in the common EIP-AGRI format. This is to facilitate more EU-wide communication related to the European Innovation Partnership on agricultural productivity and sustainability (EIP-AGRI), and the specific and cross-cutting objectives of the EU Common Agricultural Policy (CAP).

Furthermore (where applicable), it is strongly recommended to involve partners from EIP-AGRI Operational Groups (OG) funded under CAP Strategic Plans (formerly Rural Development Programmes) in Horizon Europe multi-actor projects.

3 What types of Horizon Europe projects is the multi-actor approach applied to?

Application of the multi-actor approach may be included as a specific condition for all three main types of Horizon Europe research and innovation action:

- Research and Innovation Actions (RIAs);
- Innovation Actions (IAs), and;
- Coordination and Support Actions (CSAs).

The Cluster 6 (Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment) Work Programme includes four specific types of CSA associated with Strengthening Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) which are exclusively multi-actor:

- Thematic networks (TN) as Open Calls with no pre-defined themes to compile and share knowledge ready for practice
- Thematic networks with pre-defined themes (e.g. organic farming) to compile and share knowledge ready for practice
- Thematic networks that broaden EIP-AGRI OG outcomes across borders to compile and share knowledge ready for practice
- EU advisory networks on pre-defined themes (e.g. sustainable livestock systems) that connect advisors across all EU Member States to exchange and share experiences

4 Is it necessary to design a separate, transversal work package for the MAA activities?

Horizon Europe project proposals that request the multi-actor approach can have a designated work package or task that ensures the application of the interactive innovation approach throughout the project's lifetime, but it is not obligatory.

Since a consequent application of the multi-actor approach pervades all dimensions of the work plan, each section of a multi-actor project proposal will document the different dimensions of the multi-actor approach. A designated multi-actor task or work package can include e.g. workshop facilitation services, training for the use of participatory methods, dedicated internal communication strategies, co-creative stakeholder involvement concepts or systematic piloting and validation of outputs by end-users. Moreover, regular self-reflection exercises within the consortium are relevant elements of co-innovation processes, which proposal consortia can include in their methodological foundation and work plan design.

5 I'm confused by the definition of the terms: actor, (end-)user and stakeholder in the Horizon Europe work programme. What is the difference between them?

Actors are individuals/persons or organisations taking part in project activities and contributing to project outcomes. A multi-actor project ensures the genuine and sufficient involvement of a targeted array of actors, which serves the objectives of the topic. The actors in multi-actor proposals or projects include: i) researchers, ii) farmers or farmers' groups and associations, iii) foresters/forestry groups and associations, vi) aquaculture producers, v) fishers/fishers' groups and associations, vi) advisors, vii) food and bioeconomy businesses, viii) other businesses, ix) consumer associations, x) local communities, xi) citizens, xii) civil society organisations including NGOs, and xiii) government representatives. The

relevant types of actors, which need to join the team, differ between types of projects and expected impact. Moreover, it is important to note, that actors engage with their complementary competencies from the proposal drafting to the end of project implementation and even beyond.

Moreover, project proposals for Horizon Europe Calls that require the multi-actor approach must also present how a diverse set of stakeholders, end-users and users of the project results will be involved.

Stakeholders are individuals/persons or groups served by, affected by, or with a legitimate interest (or stake) at a certain moment in time of the project work, while (end-)users are individuals/persons who ultimately use or are intended to use a product or service, which means (end-)user of projects are putting the project results into practice.

6 Is the establishment of a stakeholder advisory board or stakeholder platform sufficient to meet the specific requirements for multi-actor projects?

Stakeholder boards or platforms can be part of a project's multi-actor approach but not only. Instead, a multi-actor project is required to ensure the genuine and sufficient involvement of a targeted array of actors, which serves the objectives of the topic. The co-innovation among the project's actors should take place over the whole course of the project: from participation in developing the project idea, planning and experiments to implementation, communication and dissemination of results to a possible demonstration phase. The aim of the collaboration between the actors selected and their cross-fertilisation of skills, competencies and ideas in the project is to generate innovative and practical solutions that are likely to be applied widely by (end-)users in practice.

For that reason, the design of a stakeholder advisory board or a stakeholder platform with different relevant stakeholders engaging with the project team can be one of several measures to ensure the application of the multi-actor approach. The involvement of stakeholders from practice as

representatives of different (end-)user groups can contribute substantially to reaching the project's objectives. However, it is far from sufficient on its own. More information about the co-creation of multi-actor project results is [here](#).

7 Do Horizon Europe Multi-Actor projects require the creation of practice abstracts (PA)?

Multi-actor projects funded under EU Research and Innovation Programmes (Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe) as well as EIP-AGRI Operational Group projects supported under the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) are required to complete the EIP-AGRI common format, which includes a project profile and practice abstract(s) (PAs).

Practice abstracts are concise summaries presenting new knowledge or innovative solutions generated by the projects, tailored for practitioners as (end)-users of the projects' outputs.

Using a common format for practice-oriented projects simplifies communication about these projects and their results across regional, national and sectoral borders. The common format gives visibility to involved actors, helps measure impact and rewards researchers' work for practice-oriented work analogous to research abstracts in peer-reviewed journals.

Each Horizon Europe multi-actor project is required to develop an 'appropriate' number of PAs in the common EIP-AGRI format. What is 'appropriate' will depend on the size and subject of the multi-actor project. Some Horizon Europe Topics call for multi-actor project proposals with statements like "as many as possible", or "as many as necessary". The idea of such requirements is to share the envisaged project results with (end)-users in an easily understandable way.

The common format allows for providing information throughout the project's lifecycle. Consortia are strongly recommended to submit the first

version of the EIP-AGRI common format PAs with key project information at the beginning of the project. The idea is to facilitate networking with the EIP-AGRI/AKIS community across Europe including OGs.

PAs need to be uploaded using an online form, which is accessible via the EU CAP Network website using the EU online platform login. More information [about EU Login is here](#) , and a detailed [Horizon Europe project user guide is here](#).

Questions focusing on the role of EIP-AGRI Operational Groups (OG) in Horizon Europe multi-actor projects

8 Who retains ownership of the outputs resulting from co-creation in a Horizon Europe multi-actor project?

The ownership of results arising from the co-creation processes in a Horizon Europe project is governed by the project's Grant Agreement and the customised Consortium Agreement. Together, these define the rules on intellectual property (IP) and management of results and aim to ensure that all partners' contributions and interests are fairly managed.

The Grant Agreement requires the protection and exploitation of project results, which includes ensuring that all partners involved benefit from the innovations generated. Results are defined in the Grant Agreement as any output generated by a project, such as data, knowledge, or inventions, and are owned by the partner who generates them. If results are jointly generated and the partners' contributions cannot be individually distinguished and separated, then joint ownership applies.

The default position under Horizon Europe for joint ownership is that each joint owner can use the jointly owned results independently (for research purposes) but needs consent or compensation to commercialize or transfer them. However, multi-actor consortia can define specific rules for joint ownership in the Consortium Agreement and are encouraged to do so where high levels of co-creation are anticipated. This is especially

important to address the fair treatment of non-research participants (e.g. citizens, NGOs, SMEs) that are a critical part of the co-creation process.

9 Does implementing the multi-actor approach in Horizon projects require the involvement of EIP-AGRI OGs?

An Operational Group (OG) may include various actors from European Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS), including farmers, foresters, researchers, advisors, businesses, environmental groups, consumer interest groups or other NGOs. OGs aim to advance innovation in agriculture, forestry and rural areas in a defined spatial area. More than 3,400 EIP-AGRI Operational Groups have been established since 2014, and over 6,600 OGs are planned for the period 2023-2027.

The implementation of the MAA in Horizon projects does not require the involvement of EIP-AGRI OGs funded under the CAP Strategic Plans (former Rural Development Plans) unless explicitly mentioned in the Call Topic text. However, where applicable, it is strongly recommended that consortia involve members of interactive innovation groups, such as EIP-AGRI OGs, as they can enhance the required genuine and sufficient involvement of the (end)-user.

In the ‘Scope’ section of some MAA project Call Topics, the recommendation to involve OGs is specifically highlighted based on the need a) to capitalise and build on outputs of relevant EIP-AGRI Operational Groups and/or b) to provide details on how further synergies will be built with future OGs or other interactive innovation groups operating in this context.

10 Do EIP-AGRI Operational Groups also apply the multi-actor approach?

Yes, they do – but on a different scale and using a slightly different terminology. In contrast to Horizon Europe research and innovation projects, which are large-scale and transnational involving a minimum of three Member States (but usually many more!), EIP-AGRI Operational

Group projects are significantly smaller local/regional/national innovation projects, which seldom (with a few exceptions) work across national borders.

Nonetheless, both types of projects apply the same ‘open innovation’ concept based on the interactive innovation model, which “enhances the collaboration between actors to make best use of complementary knowledge with a view to spreading solutions ready for practice”. In accordance with Article 127(3) of the CAP Strategic Plan Regulation (EU) 2021/2115, “the interactive innovation model has three key principles:

- a) developing innovative solutions focusing on farmers’ or foresters’ needs while also tackling the interactions across the whole supply chain where useful;
- b) bringing together partners with complementary knowledge such as farmers, advisors, researchers, enterprises or non-governmental organisations in a targeted combination as best suited to achieve the project objectives, and;
- c) co-deciding and co-creating all along the project”.

II Is the multi-actor approach similar to the living lab approach?

Since the concept of ‘Living labs’ first emerged in the 1990s, they have been used in many different formats in a variety of sectors across the world. In a rural context, Living labs can be broadly defined as initiatives, in which research/experimentation is conducted on real farms, forests, landscapes, and others, in specific territorial and community contexts, with farmers and other actors involved from the beginning as equal partners with scientists in proposing ideas, testing them, improving them and promoting them further.

The European Commission DG AGRI has programmed the use of Horizon Europe funding to support the Living lab approach for driving long-term multi-actor collaborations and accelerating innovation in two specific initiatives: the Soil Deal for Europe Mission and the Agroecology

Partnership. Several individual Horizon research and innovation projects have also chosen to use the Living lab approach for experimenting and testing solutions with diverse actors living and working in real-life situations.

Living labs are, therefore, a form of the multi-actor approach that has been adapted for specific applications and purposes within Horizon Europe.

CAP-funded EIP-AGRI Operational Groups are rather more distinct from Living labs. Whilst both build on the multi-actor approach, Living labs significantly extend the dimensions of the multi-actor approach in terms of time (beyond the short timeframe of a project), place (involving multiple sites) and content (often transdisciplinary, including a Social Sciences and Humanities component). Nonetheless, they remain highly compatible, and Horizon-funded Living labs are expected to cooperate with EIP-AGRI Operational Groups (where applicable) to promote the involvement of key local stakeholders in Living lab activities and/or in disseminating solutions.

Questions focusing on aspects related to the financial administration of multi-actor projects

12 How to remunerate the active involvement of practice-oriented actors in multi-actor projects?

There is no one standard model for the financial remuneration of practitioners in multi-actor projects. The type of financial involvement depends on the degree of actors' involvement, and the needs or financial capacities of the different individuals/organisations.

Horizon Europe offers a variety of administrative rules for the remuneration of project participants. These financial rules apply to academic and non-academic partners similarly. However, some of the financial support mechanisms are more suitable for practice-oriented

actors than others because these actors might have less experience in EU-project administration or lack the administrative capacities to comply.

The highest level of integration for non-academic partners in a multi-actor consortium is the involvement as full partners in the project proposal and – in case of funding – in the Grant Agreement. A full partnership is a convincing concept for the application of the multi-actor approach. However, other forms of financial remuneration such as the involvement of Third Parties, Subcontractors or ‘Other Direct Cost’ contractors can also be appropriate given the individual needs, administrative limitations or role of the particular actor or stakeholder in the work plan. If chosen, these three funding models are part of the proposal’s financial plan. They are often also negotiated during the Grant Agreement Preparation before the project starts. While Beneficiaries (full partners) and Third Parties appear by name in the Grant Agreement already, subcontractors and contractors will be selected during the ongoing project work. Such contractual arrangements will follow the public or private procurement rules of the consortium partner in charge of their involvement.

When a Call Topic text offers the opportunity to apply the funding measure of the so-called Cascade Funding, the proposal consortium will have the opportunity to apply an advantageous model for the remuneration of actors, which will be selected and involved under simplified contractual arrangements in the project.

13 What is the difference between costs for Third Parties, subcontracting and other goods and services?

Third Parties are affiliated entities, which have a legal or financial relationship with the beneficiary and participate in the project with similar rights and obligations as the beneficiaries but do not sign the Grant Agreement and therefore do not become beneficiaries themselves.

Subcontracts concern the implementation of dedicated action tasks. Subcontracted private persons or legal entities sign a contract with one of

the Beneficiaries and are assigned a specific project activity to achieve the objectives. The selection of Subcontractors takes place during the project (not before). The Beneficiary has to demonstrate compliance with the ‘best value for money’ principle and the absence of a conflict of interest. In contrast, contracted services provide support under the supervision of the Beneficiary responsible for the specific project activity. Contracts fall under Other Direct Costs for Goods and Services.

The National Contact Points in all EU Member States provide detailed information and topic-specific advice. An EU-wide contact list is [here](#).

14 Are there any funding programmes available for the preparation of multi-actor project proposals?

For the preparation of a multi-actor project proposal, applicants do not receive financial support from the Horizon Europe Programme. However, some EU Member States offer so-called Seed Funding schemes. These programmes are country-specific and can address all types of applicants or target exclusively e.g., applied research organisations, SMEs or EIP-AGRI Operational Groups. Please, contact your national or regional agencies for further information.

Questions focusing on the evaluation of multi-actor project proposals

15 How is MAA being evaluated?

The application of the multi-actor approach in project proposals is a so-called eligibility condition highlighted in those Call topic texts that expect applicants to fulfil the particular requirements associated with the MAA. This and the other eligibility criteria are basic requirements, which are obligatory to be eligible for funding.

Since the multi-actor criterion requires a thorough study of the entire proposal text, the group of external experts are requested to address also

the multi-actor eligibility condition when evaluating the proposal text against the expectations outlined in the Call Topic text. Applicants must convince the reviewing experts by showing how their project will meet the seven key requirements for the multi-actor approach in case of funding.

The expert's assessment of the multi-actor approach refers to all sections of the proposal text: 'Excellence' with objectives and methodologies, 'Impact' addressing communication, dissemination, exploitation and stakeholder involvement, and 'Quality/efficiency of the Implementation' covering the work plan, distribution of responsibilities, project management and decision making. The assessment also covers the multi-actor requirement of 'appropriate funding' for the various types of actors involved with their complementary competencies and facilities to be used for the planned project activities.

There is no standard evaluation model because scope and expected outcome as well as particular requirements mentioned in the call topic text vary. Overall, proposals should emphasise inter- and transdisciplinarity and showcase the complementary knowledge (scientific and practical) available in the consortium. The specific methodologies or tools and the concrete activities ensuring multi-actor co-creation are expected to deliver an application of the multi-actor approach throughout the lifetime of the project. The participatory and co-innovative methods apply to the project's multi-actor setting and the involvement of external stakeholders.

The distribution of evaluation scores depends on the specific requirements outlined in the Call Topic text and the shortcomings or weaknesses identified by the reviewers. The need to address certain requirements in the different sections of the given proposal template applies to the multi-actor approach and to the other requirements outlined in the Call Topic text. All EU Member States have National Contact Points for the funding schemes of Horizon Europe, which provide information on Call Topics.

16 What type of guidance is provided to evaluators to assess the multi-actor approach in project proposals?

The EC provides a range of support material and resources for evaluators (also called ‘reviewers’ or ‘experts’) who assess the proposals submitted to EU funding programmes. The support material and resources are designed to ensure that evaluators develop a thorough understanding of the evaluation criteria, processes, and the specific requirements associated with the particular call topic. Such briefing includes the application of the multi-actor approach.

More information on the evaluation process is available [here](#).

Key support measures for reviewing experts include:

- [Evaluator briefings](#): Before the evaluation sessions, evaluators receive detailed briefings providing up-to-date information on the specific Call Topic for proposals, including any thematic priorities, the MAA requirements, and the assessment of the innovation potential. Briefings often cover practical details on the evaluation process such as confidentiality, conflict of interest, and the use of the evaluation tools provided by the EC.
- Evaluation grid: Alongside videos and individual briefings, evaluators can access a comprehensive set of documents and guidelines. These materials include detailed descriptions of the evaluation criteria, scoring guidelines, and examples of successful proposals. The evaluation grid is the most relevant of these materials. It details the aspects to be evaluated based on the general structure of the proposal template. Moreover, this includes specific indications in relation to the topic to be evaluated.
- Support videos for evaluators: These videos aim to guide evaluators through the evaluation process. They offer insights into the criteria, methodologies, and expectations for assessing proposals. The videos focus on specific aspects of the proposal (e.g. Open Science, Social Science and Humanities, etc.). However,

a Horizon Europe video explaining the eligibility condition of the multi-actor approach is not available.

17 Where can I find information about past and ongoing Horizon multi-actor projects

Horizon Europe evaluators are expected to assess if proposals are ‘beyond state-of-the-art’. Consequently, applicants need to show how the project proposal builds on scientific results available to date and experiences from earlier projects in this thematic field.

The easiest way to find information on past and ongoing multi-actor projects is to look at the [EIP-AGRI project database](#). This database has a filter that offers the search by ‘type of projects’. When searching for ‘*multi-actor projects*’, a list of all multi-actor projects appears that received funding from the precedent Framework Programme Horizon 2020. The search function also works for ‘Thematic Networks’, which represent a specific form of multi-actor projects. These projects collect existing knowledge and good practices on a given theme and aim to make this available in easily understandable formats for (end-)users such as farmers, foresters, advisors and others.

Another option to find information about ongoing Horizon Europe multi-actor projects is to search the [CORDIS](#) project database. Although this database does not offer a filter on multi-actor projects, many projects include the term ‘multi-actor’ as a keyword. When entering ‘multi-actor’ into the search function, projects and information on various multi-actor projects appear.

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